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Implications of overlap in tariff policy on waste management costs in Italian municipalities

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In today's race toward a more circular economy, optimization of tariff design is important for minimizing the environmental impact and costs of municipal waste management. This study examines the overlap of an incentive-based tariff method and the unit pricing system. We address whether this overlap impacts the effectiveness and efficiency of waste management in Italian municipalities. Based on a panel data sample for 5,512 municipalities from 2016 to 2022, a generalized method of moments estimation was employed for a linear dynamic panel model. The results suggest that there is room for optimizing their overlap under certain circumstances—specifically, when the availability of waste treatment facilities is adequate and the percentage of separate waste collection is high. The interaction between the percentage of separate collection and the incentive tariff method contributed to cost reduction, confirming the need for consistency and compatibility of a tariff scheme with circular economy objectives. The effective adoption of both tools, as well as other actions such as information campaigns and service delivery improvements, can promote waste sorting and investment in management facilities. The results provide insights for policymakers seeking to design more effective and efficient policy measures aimed at maximizing environmental effectiveness, in accordance with the polluter-pays principle, and minimizing costs.

1. Introduction

The efficient management of municipal waste requires effective and sustainable charging schemes. To this end, the integration of incentives into waste management charging can improve service delivery efficiency and increase citizens' engagement. The consequent effects on reduction, separate collection, and recycling offer insights useful for formulating policies aimed at reducing costs and increasing environmental sustainability (Chu and Sappington 2012).

Challenging environmental targets are paving the way for cleaner service delivery, pushing policymakers to design circular economy (CE) measures such as regulatory and policy tools. However, the growing corpus of legislation introduces the potential problem of overlapping policy tools, as in other energy and environmental markets. Policy overlapping can bring both opportunities—as it can spur innovation in specific sectors (Palage *et al* 2018)—and risks that can lead to suboptimal outcomes. The management of such risks is necessary to avoid or mitigate suboptimal effects (Saidi and Spray 2018) of complementary tools with desirable aims.

This study analyzes the implications of tariff policies by examining how the interaction between various schemes can influence the effectiveness of municipal solid waste (MSW) management. Through an empirical analysis of municipal-level data, we provide useful insights for policymakers seeking to design more efficient strategies consistent with CE goals. Insights from this study are relevant given that MSW management is one of the most important and rapidly evolving municipal services in light of CE targets (Beccarello and Di Foggia 2023).

Previous literature has analyzed effects of overlapping regulation in the carbon market (Böhringer *et al* 2007). This study empirically examines, in the waste management context, the potential impact of the overlapping of an incentive-based waste management tariff scheme (TM) and the unit pricing (UP) that can be used as the default pricing approach within such tariff schemes. We highlight how the role of UP can vary depending on local treatment capacity, territorial characteristics, and environmental performance. We argue that in some circumstances, comparable improvements in waste management outcomes can be achieved through alternative instruments tailored to local conditions.

We perform empirical analysis based on a panel data sample containing information from 5,512 Italian municipalities from 2016 to 2022. The research design involves a mixed method approach consisting of group comparisons and panel data econometric analysis, namely, generalized method of moments (GMM) estimation for a linear dynamic panel model.

We aim to address the problem of the overlap between alternative policies given that the recent regulatory framework introduced in the country serves as an interesting case. This paper's innovative aspect lies in its analysis of this regulation, highlighting challenges it presents in reconciling different policy approaches. We fill a gap in existing literature by exploring the practical implications and the effectiveness of such regulatory frameworks. We highlight that overlapping policies can sometimes lead to suboptimal outcomes in MSW management, emphasizing the need for coordinated policies to enhance economic and environmental efficiency.

Evidence confirms a potential suboptimal outcome when the UP and TM overlap, while the interaction between the sorting share and TM reveals that the higher the sorting share, the lower the cost. Consistent with CE compliance principles, this evidence can guide policymakers toward more effective and cost-efficient choices. The UP and TM can still be employed together, provided that the underlying conditions are duly controlled for. The UP is particularly useful in areas with significant potential for improvement of performance in separate waste collection; in these areas, investments in waste treatment capacity are essential. Instead, when separate waste collection rates are high and adequate facilities are available, alternative policies can be adopted.

In order to meet circularity targets such as maximizing recycling and minimizing landfill usage, new policies and regulations are being issued worldwide and numerous existing policies are being upgraded.

2. Theoretical context

The principle behind modern waste management charging schemes is to go beyond the parameters underlying traditional models, which typically include the size and the number of residents per household (Welivita *et al* 2015, Alzamora and Barros 2020). Although these parameters are good proxies for waste generation, they do not comply with the pillar of environmental legislation, namely, the polluter-pays principle (Morlok *et al* 2017).

Moreover, it is necessary to evaluate and optimize the quantity and quality of waste produced by citizens (Elia *et al* 2015); with this in mind, pricing systems can be designed with incentive schemes that induce citizens to actively contribute to moving toward CE. The economic literature on the effectiveness of waste management tariffs has grown (Bohm *et al* 2010, Sarra *et al* 2017) and focuses strongly on environmental sustainability (Chamizo-González *et al* 2018). We argue that in the light of environmental objectives and, in particular, CE targets, economic efficiency is highly dependent on prevailing regulation because effective economic regulation improves the competitive environment by inducing service operators to improve their performance (Kitching *et al* 2013).

Indeed, robust waste management economic regulation is necessary because the sector may be subject to inefficient conditions due to monopoly issues, market failure, and a lack of incentives. Considering that regulating the company's revenues is likely to be the most common approach (Simões and Marques 2012), translating this principle to citizens in terms of rewards presents a key challenge. Numerous studies have investigated technical regulation and presented the consequent implications on the qualitative and technical aspects of waste management (Bárcena-Ruiz and Casado-Izaga 2015, Chalak *et al* 2016).

International comparisons of the regulatory framework are also considered for potential improvements (Jaccoud and Magrini 2014), including the relationship between policy and practice and its suitability and applicability (Muheirwe *et al* 2022). However, this remains a rather complex issue owing to the different reference contexts. Nevertheless, efficient waste management cannot exist without a reliable regulatory framework (Rodić and Wilson 2017).

Europe's CE targets call for 65% of municipal solid waste to be recycled and less than 10% disposed in landfills by 2035 (Camana *et al* 2021). Previous literature has analyzed the determinants and performance of the CE to assess the progress toward achieving these targets (Marino and Pariso 2020, Robaina *et al* 2020). It has been reported that only some of the development strategies adopted can be considered effective in achieving EU standards (Mazur-Wierzbicka 2021). Furthermore, D'Adamo *et al* (2022) suggest that policymakers should

urgently focus on policy implications to accelerate convergence toward the goals. It is worth noting that the level of circularity is influenced by socioeconomic factors, including environmental taxes and R&D expenditures (Kostakis and Tsagarakis 2021).

In contrast, tariffs can lead to economic and environmental efficiency (Brown *et al* 2015) and increase user participation by rewarding the virtuous behavior (Di Foggia and Beccarello 2021) of those who choose recyclable materials and reduce residual waste (Lakhan 2015). Scholars have identified the positive externalities associated with the UP (Slučiaková 2021), such as increased separate collection, reduced waste production, unsorted waste per capita, and the positive repercussions regarding image and reputation (Dahlén and Lagerkvist 2010, Romano and Masserini 2023). It is also important to assess environmental performance in terms of the quality and level of sorted waste, as the evolution toward advanced tariff structure mechanisms coincides with the objectives of the CE (D'Onza *et al* 2016).

Empirically, research has suggested that UP schemes help to reduce the amount of waste produced, among other environmental benefits (Romano and Masserini 2023), and that the UP has led to a significant increase in the recycling rate and reduction in the amount of residual waste. Scholars also indicate that feed-in tariffs can help reduce the amount of unsorted waste, but do not increase recycling (Huang *et al* 2020); meanwhile, others associate such tariffs with a 20% waste reduction (Dahlén and Lagerkvist 2010). Figure 1 resumes the approach. It begins with the policy goal of enhancing waste management, followed by the role of tariffs in incentivizing goals and controlling costs. The evolution section shows the transition toward a new tariff structure with incentives. After that, it highlights the potential overlap and concludes that alternative tools could also positively concur to improve the sector.

Italy's municipal solid waste charging system has evolved considerably over the year and particularly important for this study from the Italian Regulatory Authority for Energy, Networks and Environment (ARERA) Resolution 443/2019/R/Rif and upgrades. The tariff scheme, which was established to cover the waste management service costs, is divided into fixed (FC) and variable (VC) components according to the sub-services related to the cost. TF covers the costs as specified in equation (1) where *swc* denotes the cost of sweeping and washing streets and squares; *cc* refers to general costs; *adm* indicates the cost of administrative activities for assessments, tax collection, and litigation management; *man* represents the general operating costs; *other* includes typical miscellaneous costs; and *ck* is the cost of capital use.

$$FC = swc + cc + adm + man + other + ck, \quad (1)$$

Similarly, VC is described by equation (2) where *ctcx* is the cost of the collection and transport of municipal solid waste; *disp* is the cost of waste treatment and disposal; *recc* is the cost of the collection and transport of recyclable materials, namely, separate collection; and *rect* is the cost of the treatment and recycling of materials (net of revenues from the sale of materials and energy from waste).

$$VC = ctcx + disp + recc + rect \quad (2)$$

The price cap formula presented in equation (3), where inf_t is planned inflation and X_t is the productivity recovery for the base year, has historically governed the annual tariff increase.

$$T_t = T_{t-1} * (1 + inf_t - X_t), \quad (3)$$

This configuration also aims to encourage citizens and businesses to minimize waste production, allowing them to gain by reducing the amount of unsorted waste in favor of sorted waste, leading to significant savings. This consequently incentivizes both citizens and businesses to reduce or avoid producing waste. This principle finds its place in the incentive tariff scheme through the introduction of three components. The first component γ determined by multiplying revenue distribution factor with revenues from materials and energy. The second component δ is the revenue distribution factor of the material revenues multiplied by the revenues from the National Packaging Consortium. The third component, θ is determined by multiplying the efficient costs by the adjustment component related to variable costs and dividing by the number of installments for the equalization of adjustment component. In addition to the aforementioned components, the factor *cimp* is intended to cover the expected variable costs related to achieving quality improvements or changes in the management perimeter.

See the ARERA Resolution 443/2019/R/Rif and the following for additional information on the tariff scheme. The above components can be used to express the fixed and variable components of the tariff. Equation (4) describes the fixed component of the TM.

$$FC_{ce} = swc + cc + ck + cimp + \theta. \tag{4}$$

Similarly, the variable component can be expressed using equation (5), from which the role of the incentivizing factors can be observed.

$$VC_{ce} = VC + cimp - \gamma - \delta + \theta. \tag{5}$$

Based on this, the price cap is defined in equation (6). In this case, there are two new components: Q , which represents the expected improvement in the quality and characteristics of the service; and S , which denotes the change in the scope of service.

$$T_t \leq T_{t-1}(1 + inf - X + Q + S). \tag{6}$$

The tariff structure, including the elements that make up the price cap mechanism, has evolved to incentivize both citizens and businesses to operate efficiently such that they can earn economic rewards related to environmental performance.

3. Research design and methods

In advanced economies, waste management charging schemes are typically aimed at full-cost recovery, economic efficiency, and promoting the polluter-pays principle consistently, under a CE perspective. The TM is in line with the principles of CE, and provides incentives to increase the rate of separate collection. This study aims to test the hypothesis that if the waste sorting rate is high, simultaneous adoption of the UP may be unnecessary owing to its implementation and management costs. Indeed, the expected savings are achievable, provided waste treatment and disposal capacity is adequate. This is also indicated in figure 2, which summarizes the waste management chain and phases.

The chain includes two main phases: (a) the labor-intensive collection and transport phase, typically a legal monopoly; and (b) treatment and disposal, which comprise both regulated and non-regulated activities and services. The UP incentivizes waste sorting, and, therefore, citizens can benefit from good performance—namely, the smaller the residual share of waste generated, the lower the amount to pay. Figure 2 also shows that the same result can be achieved by combining command and control principles with market-based mechanisms. This can also be seen from a regulatory perspective, as shown in figure 3, in which the tariff includes regulated and free market services.

European CE targets require countries to limit their share of municipal solid waste to 10% as a maximum and increase their recycling share to 70% by 2035. Meeting such challenging goals requires sound policymaking

that aims to improve accessibility, economic efficiency, usability, adequate quality levels in management efficiency and cost-effectiveness conditions, and infrastructural adaptation.

This paper refers to Italy and it is worth noting that Chien *et al* (2023) offer valuable insights into the challenges and opportunities associated with solid waste management in emerging economies. These serve as a functional comparative basis for understanding similar dynamics in other contexts while Hao *et al* (2024) introduce innovative perspectives by examining the role of the digital economy in advancing zero-waste city initiatives.

Based on the above information, we address the following research question: Does this overlap impact the effectiveness and efficiency of waste management in Italian municipalities? Answering this question inform policy decisions aimed at improving the circularity of the industry.

4. Data sample, variables, and model

Detailed information on waste was obtained from the Waste Cadastre of the Environmental Protection Institute, and relevant geographic data were sourced from the Institute of Statistics. The data sample covers 5,512 Italian municipalities from 2016 to 2022. Provided that many variables can affect the eco-efficiency of MSW (Io Storto 2024), table 1 presents the descriptive statistics of the variables used in the model. In more details, UP refers to unit pricing, TM denotes the incentive-based waste management tariff, RE is the total municipal revenue, WG represents the municipal waste per capita, IN is the harmonized index of consumer prices, CV is a dummy variable to mark the pandemic upsurge, DE stands for population density, SH is the share of sorted waste, ALT is the altitude, SEA denotes coastal municipalities, PR indicates the proximity of waste treatment, TC is the total cost of municipal waste management, CTCX refers to the collection cost for municipal waste, CTCU is the unsorted waste collection cost, and CTCS denotes the sorted waste collection cost.

Table 2 Presents the correlation matrix for the independent variables included in the econometric model and the correlation coefficients suggest that there are no issues of multicollinearity.

The empirical study is performed to determine: 1) whether the introduction of the UP has increased the percentage of separately collected waste; 2) the evolution of waste generation; and 3) the degree of influence of the simultaneous implementation of the UP and TM on waste reduction behavior. It is argued that, in some cases, the simultaneous application of these tools can lead to increased costs. Introducing the UP in areas where the percentage of separate waste collection is already high can lead to marginal improvement. In contrast, in less virtuous contexts, where separate waste collection is less developed, the UP can act as a powerful incentive to improve waste management practices. An econometric model was used with panel data to test our hypotheses. Using a panel data model allows us to exploit both the temporal and cross-sectional variability of the data, which improves the efficiency of the estimates and yields more robust inferences. The general formula of the panel data model is formalized in equation (7):

$$Y_{it} = \alpha + \beta X_{it} + \mu_i + \lambda_t + \epsilon_{it}, \quad (7)$$

Table 1. Descriptive statistics.

Variable	Obs.	Mean	SD	Min	Max
UP	31,294	0.139	0.346	0	1
TM	31,294	0.743	0.889	0	2
REV	30,613	2251	2,143	0	69,407
WG	31,183	462.3	168.1	41	3,213
IN	31,294	113.4	5.4	104	121.4
CV	31,294	1.144	0.351	1	2
DE	31,267	395.4	749.6	2.1	12,119
SH	31,191	0.651	0.184	0.2	95.1
ALT	31,267	313.6	278.8	0	1,816
SEA	31,267	0.091	0.288	0	1
PR	31,294	0.409	0.189	0.17	1.74
TC	31,294	157.4	81.78	15.65	1,670
CTCX	31,294	64.53	39.93	0	796.7
CTCU	30,332	24.32	26.55	0	549.4
CTCS	30,190	42.45	29.29	0	603.8

Variables: UP, dummy; TM, before 0, year 1, after 2; REV, euro per capita; WG, kg per capita; IN, index; CV, dummy—1 yes, 0 no; DE, inhabitants per km²; SH, %; ALT, meters above sea level (m.a.s.l); SEA—dummy 1 yes, 0 no; PR, % of MSW; TC, euro per capita; CTCX, euro per capita; CTCU, euro per capita; CTCS, euro per capita.

Source: the authors

Table 2. Correlation between the independent variables used in the model.

	RE	WG	IN	DE	SH	ALT	SEA	PR
RE	1							
WG	0.142	1						
IN	0.1538	0.0252	1					
DE	-0.1456	0.026	-0.0141	1				
SH	-0.1394	-0.0604	0.1869	0.0634	1			
ALT	0.3871	-0.1279	-0.0016	-0.257	-0.2564	1		
SEA	0.0884	0.2663	0.014	0.0762	-0.1354	-0.2397	1	
PR	-0.0164	-0.0694	-0.0752	-0.0393	-0.1937	0.1462	0.0016	1

Source: the authors

where Y_{it} is the dependent variable for unit i at time t ; α is the intercept; β is the vector of the coefficients of the independent variables; X_{it} is the vector of independent variables for unit i at time t ; μ_i represents unit-specific effects; λ_t represents time-specific effects; and ϵ_{it} is the idiosyncratic error. The econometric model used in our study is defined in equation (8), which is replicated in four versions according to the dependent variable under investigation (table 3). The econometric approach utilizes GMM estimation for a linear dynamic panel model Baltagi *et al* (2016). This method has the advantage of combining traditional linear moment conditions with nonlinear moment conditions, assuming the presence of serially uncorrelated idiosyncratic errors.

$$\begin{aligned}
 TC_{it} = & \alpha + \beta_1 TC_{it-1} + \beta_2 UP_{it} + \beta_3 TM_{it} + \beta_4 RE_{it} + \beta_5 WG_{it} + \beta_6 IN_{it} \\
 & + \beta_7 CV_{it} + \beta_8 DE_{it} + \beta_9 SH_{it} + \beta_{10} ALT_{it} + \beta_{11} SEA_{it} + \beta_{12} PR_{it} \\
 & + \beta_{13} UP_{it} \times TM_{it} + \beta_{14} SH_{it} \times TM_{it} + \mu_i + \lambda_t + \epsilon_{it}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Equation (8) incorporates both the long-run equilibrium relation and short-run dynamics, better explaining the dynamics underlying waste management costs and identify the most effective policies for their reduction. The consistency of the GMM specifications depends on the validity of the instruments in the estimation process (Blundell *et al* 2001), the first and second-order serial correlation test errors, and orthogonality conditions.

5. Empirical results

A key goal of regulation is to maximize environmental performance while minimizing costs. In this context, figure 4 presents interesting insights into differences in environmental performance before, i.e., Group 1 (G1) and after, i.e., Group 2 (G2) implementation of the TM.

Table 3. Regression results.

Variable	TC	CTCX	CTCU	CTCS
UP	-0.0151*** (0.00337)	-0.0414*** (0.00725)	-0.0526*** (0.0117)	-0.0592*** (0.0107)
TM	0.871*** (0.0793)	0.994*** (0.133)	0.487*** (0.180)	1.259*** (0.188)
RE	0.0129*** (0.00353)	0.0296*** (0.0104)	0.0656*** (0.0137)	0.0217 (0.0139)
WG	0.0406*** (0.00574)	0.0930*** (0.00917)	0.0696*** (0.0132)	0.144*** (0.0138)
IN	-0.0198*** (0.00187)	-0.0216*** (0.00316)	-0.00770* (0.00414)	-0.0293*** (0.00443)
CV	0.758*** (0.0684)	0.855*** (0.115)	0.252 (0.154)	1.039*** (0.164)
DE	-0.00272*** (0.000778)	-0.0104*** (0.00220)	-0.0156*** (0.00314)	-0.00923*** (0.00304)
SH	-0.0426*** (0.0123)	0.00841 (0.0295)	-0.272*** (0.0443)	0.297*** (0.0484)
ALT	-0.00155** (0.000706)	-0.000471 (0.00193)	-0.00175 (0.00266)	-0.00202 (0.00260)
SEA	0.0130*** (0.00355)	0.0812*** (0.00969)	0.0623*** (0.0141)	0.119*** (0.0133)
PR	-0.0133*** (0.00483)	-0.00734 (0.0138)	-0.0729*** (0.0192)	0.0505** (0.0203)
UP-TM	0.00748** (0.00305)	0.0212*** (0.00743)	0.0449*** (0.0104)	0.00323 (0.0103)
SH-TM	-0.0270** (0.0137)	-0.116*** (0.0326)	-0.201*** (0.0455)	-0.199*** (0.0455)
L.TC	0.930*** (0.00477)			
L.CTCX		0.795*** (0.0100)		
L.CTCU			0.752*** (0.0113)	
L.CTCS				0.741*** (0.0142)
Time effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Obs.	23602	23477	22679	22451
Number of municipalities	5264	5252	5185	5162

Robust standard errors in parentheses; *** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, * p < 0.1. TC refers to the total cost of waste management and the following three columns refer to the collection: CTCX refers to all waste, CTCU refers to unsorted waste, and CTCS refers to sorted waste.

Source: the authors.

As Panel A of figure 4 shows, the average sorting rate in G2 is 68.63%, exceeding that of G1 (62.59%). Similarly, focusing on per capita waste generation, the statistical analysis presented in Panel B indicates that the mean for G2 is higher than that of G1. This difference can be attributed to the difference in the number of observations between the groups and the distinct temporal contexts. In terms of the econometric analysis, the results of the model formalized in equation (8) are reported in table 3, with four versions presented based on the iteration purpose.

As table 3 indicates, the average cost is lower in municipalities with a UP system (-0.0151), confirming that UP can reduce waste management costs. In contrast, the new tariff method may have led to an initial cost increase. This can be attributed to the initial easing of the price cap, the discrepancies in recognized costs compared with previous periods, and the occurrence of the pandemic, causing the increase in production input costs, the energy crises due to geopolitical tensions, and transition costs resulting from the switch to the new system.

A positive coefficient is determined for the UP-TM interaction, suggesting that, although both systems aim to reduce costs through efficiency mechanisms, their overlap may not be as effective, in terms of cost reduction, as expected. The sorting share exerts a negative impact, and the interaction between the percentage of separate collection and the new regulatory method SH-TM also has a negative coefficient. This indicates that combining a high separate collection percentage with the TM leads to a reduction in costs, further strengthening the

argument that waste treatment capacity is a crucial factor in meeting CE targets. However, political decision-makers and regulatory authorities must adequately analyze the overlap between the tariff and the new regulatory method.

Population density and the harmonized index of consumer prices for waste also affect the total cost. In particular, population density is related to the optimization of collection and transport operations. Moreover, the general price increase has induced local authorities and firms to minimize the costs resulting from the rise in production input prices, particularly for energy. Indeed, the pandemic has had a significant positive impact. These results confirm that adopting a UP reduces waste management costs, whereas introducing the new regulatory method entails higher initial costs. The overlap of these two systems does not appear to be effective, given that the CE targets internalized in the TM can be achieved through other drivers: for example, a high separate collection percentage combined with a good regional waste treatment capacity contributes most to cost reduction.

We also analyze how the variables influence the collection phase, namely, the first stage in figure 2. Consistent with expectations, waste production has a significantly higher impact on collection and transport costs, suggesting that the increase in waste generates higher costs, mainly in the collection phase. The negative impact of inflation is similar in both models but slightly stronger on collection and transportation costs. This indicates a more significant efficiency effort in this phase, which is most strongly influenced by fuel costs and labor intensive. The pandemic has increased costs in both categories, with a slightly more significant impact on collection and transportation costs, reflecting the increased health and operational measures required during the pandemic. Population density has a more pronounced negative impact on collection and transportation costs, suggesting that densely populated areas benefit from economies of scale. Although separate waste collection reduces total costs due to revenues from material selling, it appears to slightly increase collection and transport costs because of the need to organize a specific collection and transport service.

In contrast, the collection and transport of undifferentiated waste exhibit higher economies of scale. Altitude has a minimal negative impact on both costs, while being a coastal municipality increases collection and transportation costs more than total costs because of specific logistical challenges in tourist-dominated coastal areas, especially in the summer. Consistent with expectations, waste treatment capacity reduces total costs more than collection and transportation costs. This indicates that a higher treatment capacity significantly reduces overall costs because of the lesser need to transport waste to other regions, which incurs increased costs from logistics and taxation. The overlapping of the UP and TM increases collection and transportation costs more than total costs, while the interaction between separate collection and TM reduces costs in both categories, significantly affecting collection and transport costs. This reinforces the idea that efforts and policies aimed at increasing the share of sorted waste may be effective within a TM framework, consistent with the polluter-pays principle and CE.

Although the overlap between the UP and TM may lead to unexpected economic results, this does not imply that these instruments should not be used together. Rather, it suggests that the underlying conditions need to be verified. The UP system can greatly contribute in areas where the separate collection rate is average, encouraging people to sort more waste and leading policymakers to boost the CE industry. This paves the way for investments

and efforts to equip the area with facilities to handle the separated waste. When the percentage of sorted waste is already very high, and the territory has separate waste management facilities, alternative policies can be adopted too.

Practical implications suggest adapting policies to local conditions. Service optimization can be incentivized through a range of complementary tools and policies. As follows some examples: smart bins equipped with sensors that monitor fill level, allowing more efficient collection and reducing transportation costs, reverse vending machines installed in strategic points that accept plastic bottles or cans and return credits or discounts, integration of deposit systems on certain materials, refundable upon return, recycling and collection applications that educate and assist citizens in properly sorting waste, geolocation systems for mobile ecological islands to improve service in remote areas or areas with inadequate collection, repair or reuse centers linked to collection points, education, communication and training of the citizenry through interactive platforms, innovative household composters for processing organic waste.

Although results are inspiring, this study has limitations, too. It covers a medium-term period, though a more extended timeframe would be preferable for more robust conclusions. Also, it does not analyze the impact of alternative policies, such as service cost efficiency measures or the adoption of new technologies, particularly in the waste collection phase. Additionally, municipalities implementing UP remain relatively few and are primarily geographically concentrated, limiting the range of the sample.

6. Conclusions

This study has focused on the importance of aligning tariff design with circular economy goals to optimize waste management outcomes. The findings suggest the importance of well-coordinated policies to maximize economic and environmental efficiency in waste management. Economic effectiveness depends on the specific context: in cases where waste treatment and disposal capacity are adequate, overlapping among policies can reduce benefits of policies that if applied independently could outperform their marginal contribution in a policy mix. This suggests that policies must be adapted to local conditions in order to maximize their effectiveness. That said, the results are consistent with those of previous studies that have found that the UP can increase the rate of separate waste collection and reduce unsorted waste. In situations where, separate waste collection is already high, adapting them to avoid redundant overlapping may be more cost-effective; given this, decision-makers should evaluate the specific local context. Therefore, complementary policies can be used together if the underlying conditions are duly evaluated to maximize their role in moving toward a CE. Introducing a UP alone may not sufficient to improve waste management service quality. Therefore, by assessing the role of smart bins, reverse vending machines, deposit-refund systems, recycling apps, geolocated ecological islands, repair centers, interactive platforms, and household composters, policymakers could effectively enhance MSW sustainability. This research highlights the importance of coordinated policy planning for waste management and can be applied to other areas where multiple environmental policies interact. Future research may focus on analyzing multiple mechanisms and international comparisons to further understand the effectiveness of different policy approaches across different countries and market structures.

Declarations

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Conflicts of interest/competing interests

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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